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Abstract

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
3PL	Third Party Logistic Service Provider
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
CGO	Common Goal Orientation
CluCS	Cluster Community System
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CR	Consistency Ratio
CT	Computed Tomography
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
I	Information flow
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSP	Logistics Service Provider
MCA	Multi-criteria analysis
PO	Project officer
PTN	Proximity Terminal Network
RO	Railway Operator
SCM	Supply Chain Management
SCO	Supply Chain Orientation
SME	Small Medium-sized Enterprise
TS	Train Service
TsS	Transshipment service
TWS	Transportation-warehousing service
VALS	Value Added Logistics Service
VCM	Value Case Methodology
VCO	Vertical Cooperation Orientation
VNA	Value Network Map
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The current document is intended to provide the guidelines for Smart Cluster establishment path, including engagement of manufacturing and value-added service providers in Cluster activities and integration of them with CluCS.

The document is organized as follows:

Chapter 1 reports on the purpose of the document and the addressed audience.

Chapter 2 gives an overview on the engagement of manufacturing and value added service providers in Cluster activities and integration of them with CluCS.

In particular, it explains how to support the engagement of manufacturers and how to facilitate the value added logistics services (VALS) that can contribute to logistics flow optimization and provide benefits to all members of CluCS network. Finally, it presents a framework for the engagement of the different stakeholders in CluCS network.

Chapter 3 analyzes CluCS actors' needs adopting the Value Case Methodology (VCM): the involvement of manufacturers and VALS providers depends on the success of the established CluCS network. The analysis is based on a stakeholders' survey conducted during CluCS platform presentation event in Interporto Bologna on 12th June 2019. The survey enabled the collection of stakeholders' perspectives, barriers, demands and preferences for CluCS implementation.

The four main steps conducted in the VCM are the following:

- Value case analysis
- Value quantification analysis
- Value alignment analysis
- Business options in CluCS context

Chapter 4 defines CluCS interfaces with manufacturing and integration with value added services in Bologna PTN giving cargo pooling as experimental scenario of VALS.

Chapter 5 details Smart Clusters development path. It should be based on a synergy between the organizational innovation aspect (CluCS organizational network) and the software innovation aspect (CluCS platform).

The document is closed by chapter 6, that summarises the main findings and outcomes of the deliverable.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of Document

The document contains the guidelines outlining Smart Cluster establishment path, including engagement of manufacturing and value-added service providers in Cluster activities and integration of them with CluCS. It is devoted to support Logistics Clusters to become value creators for the region where they are formed. Once the Cluster is established, a virtuous circle is put in place increasing availability of intermodal connections and value-added services, such as co-packing and shipment consolidation, late product differentiation, assembling and testing, logistics process tracking, vehicle load factor optimisation, last mile optimisation and connections with cities, single booking window.

The document is the result of task 2.5 which deals with the involvement of local actors in Cluster activities, thus meaning the profitable engagement of manufacturing and value added service providers, also relying on CluCS capabilities for improving / enabling coordination and boosting logistics best practices such as advanced collaboration, with the final aim of minimising negative impacts such as congestion, noise, land use and local pollution.

1.2 Intended Audience

The intended audience of this document are the Clusters 2.0 project partners.

With regard to the functional aspects, the document aims to address:

- all the supply chain roles that can be involved in the development of the Cluster Community System in practical terms, with a focus on the need for collaboration in a competitive environment;
- all the actors of the supply chain that could benefit from operational advantages and positive impacts from the Cluster Community System development.

2 Engagement with manufacturing and value-added service providers [Leader: ZLC; Partners: IBI]

The main objective of CluCS platform is to increase the performance of the existing network of flows between various nodes (hubs, terminals, warehouses) within the Logistics cluster. This general objective which will lead to improvement of productivity (and therefore competitiveness and attractiveness) of the cluster as a whole is supported by the actor involved-specific effects:

- Nodes (terminals, hubs, warehouses): higher level of synchronization with other actors within the Cluster, improved throughput time which will lead to improved utilization of existing capacities, and therefore to improved productivity of terminals and hubs. Belonging to the CluCS network warehouses also improve smoothness and resilience of the inbound/outbound flows which produces improved utilization of the warehouse space and improved customer satisfaction.
- LSPs: Optimization of logistics flows improves the competitive position of the 3PLs. Rail operators should be able to provide better service in terms of saving time and reliability, visibility and flexibility. Economy of scale as a result of cargo consolidation and cargo pooling will generate improved competitiveness of LSP and potential for market uptake by the rail related actors.
- Shippers: increased reliability, flexibility, visibility, decreased lead time and cost of the service.

Certainly, the most important actors within the CluCS network are shippers. Engagement of shippers in a new cloud based collaborative ICT platform faces two challenges:

- Existing close solutions with limited connectivity aimed for specific business. Also, SMEs do not use sophisticated information systems due to their expensive costs.
- Fragmentation in IT solutions: Different user requirements, data models, system specification

and business models imply appearance of a variety of information systems.

More specifically, big manufacturers in a logistics cluster usually have their own proprietary systems closed and ad hoc solutions with a low level of openness to other systems. By the way, communication among them is often difficult due to the multiplicity of communication standards adopted by different actors. On the other side, SMEs perform their business in less efficient way since they are not able to buy expensive and sophisticated systems. Therefore, CluCS represents a mean for a smooth evolution from existing very dispersed technological panorama in a Cluster to a system based on the interconnection of a set of networks. In general, manufacturers will decide to join the collaborative ICT platform when they are expecting a supernormal profit jointly generated in an exchange relationship that cannot be generated by either firm in isolation and can only be created through the joint idiosyncratic contributions of the specific alliance partners (Dyer and Singh, 1998). CluCS collaborative booking and planning which is more proactive than traditional freight bundling fits also with Physical Internet initiatives to tackle the inefficiencies in transport and logistics activities.

2.1 Engagement of manufacturers in CluCS network

Engagement of manufacturers in this collaborative ICT platform must be bi-directionally supported. From the aspect of manufacturer supply chain orientation (SCO) is one of the crucial factors. SCO represents the recognition by an organization of the systematic, strategic implications of the tactical activities involved in managing the various flows in a supply chain (Mentzer et al., 2001; Smart-Rail, 2018). The higher the level of SCO is, the greater the level of integration of key business process across the CluCS established network becomes. SCO emphasizes the strategic awareness and embracing of Supply Chain Management (SCM) within supply chain firm as a precondition of a SCM (Esper et al., 2010). In general, SCO should be considered as the overall positive attitude of a manufacturer (and all other actors within CluCS network) towards cooperation with other actors and the recognition of common goals along the supply chain.

The willingness to implement SCM represents the instrument to measure SCO. For this purpose two concepts are considered:

- Vertical cooperation orientation (VCO): positive attitude towards collaboration with other actors;
- Common goal orientation (CGO): general positive attitude regarding the existence of mutual goals with other actors.

A combination of high VCO and high CGO should result in a greater willingness to implement SCM.

Here, the size of the manufacturer should be also considered. Large firms are more flexible in collaborative engagements, whereas the scope of the SME influence on supply chains may be more restricted. SMEs, as the majority of firms in logistics cluster, lack of essential capabilities and power to carry out SCM. Some studies have been shown that SMEs do not appear to implement SCM as deeply as large manufacturers do. In some cases, SMEs do not employ SCM, rather they are managed at arm's length by large customers. SMEs and SCM are a poor fit when SMEs have a truly independent choice, but a better fit when the choice is forced by a key partner. Therefore, in order to engage SME into the CluCS, SMEs need assistance in implementing SCM practices.

Here we come to the other direction toward the engagement of manufacturers into the IT supported collaborative network. Cluster manager should create a comprehensive engagement strategy by reviewing and aligning the motives and barriers of all actors, big firms, as well as SMEs (value alignment is the subject of the next section), and convincing them that the platform and SC-oriented approach may generate significant effects on their profitability and sustainability. Manufacturers should benefit through reduced logistics costs and negative impact of the bullwhip effect and increased service levels, market share and capacity. Engagement strategy should be materialized in a framework for setting out the strategic approach to stakeholder engagement. This framework should outline the models of engagement, key actions, capability improvement agenda, approach to risk oversight and management.

2.2 Facilitating the Value-Added Logistics Services and relationship with manufacturers

Value-added logistics services (VALS) are important for manufacturers so they can focus on their core businesses. Manufacturers in essence buy logistics flexibility that allows them to add value as late as possible in the supply chain. VALS selection depends on the manufacturer's own competence as well as the logistics flow optimization.

In a logistics cluster there is a large variety of categories of value-added services (VAS), providers of these services, potential customers (firms – big and SMEs) and customer-provider relationships. Each of them creates a specific dimension for describing the VALS provider – manufacturer situation. VALS providers have different core competences, size, relations with their customers, extent of supply chain integration. Firms are different regarding their supply chain role and their logistics competences. In general, different value-added services have different prerequisites and revenue potential. These services can be developed reactively or proactively, as a general offer or specific to some customer. In that sense it is needed to consider the current service offering process - the types of value-added service providers, customers and their relationships and to formulate a new framework for value-added service offering.

CluCS solution, by its purpose, should provide enhanced coordination among LSPs operating in the Cluster network of hubs, terminals and infrastructures. Synergy among all actors in the CluCS network will increase the efficiency of the flows within the Cluster which will positively influence on the base services (transportation and warehousing). VALS are almost always associated with the base services. This will contribute to the development of common improved value added services. VALS are linked to the process of servitisation and can add value to the product and since CluCS platform enhances coordination among the actors (improved coordination which leads to improved reliability, flexibility, cost and lead time), provision of advanced supply chain solutions can be improved. The information sharing among all actors involved in the supply chain is a key role in order to improve coordination and the absorbency of the chain. This translates into a fast and visible up-to-date information, and it can be improved through close partnership with customers and suppliers, who can help in the joint development of new products. In parallel, a joint effort in reducing the lead time and multi-directional training of the workforces are also needed.

More precisely, the value-added service providers have an opportunity to add value to products by co-packing, consolidation, late product differentiation, assembling and testing and vehicle load factor optimisation. Last mile optimisation and single booking window are also considered as added value offerings.

The primary role of CluCS is to be the general contractor for the benefit of all members of the network concerning complex activities, i.e. systems integration as a service. Each actor in the CluCS network is independent and offers different services. CluCS enables value added services thanks to the dynamic network: more, quicker and cost effective realised services and higher capacities. CluCS manager may play a facilitator role that enhances the development of collaboration practices and value added services between co-located firms.

In order to support the development of an advance value added service offering Cluster manager should promote a framework for categorizing logistic services which can be applied to design proper logistics service model for customers (large firms as well as SMEs). This framework should take into account the perspective of firms as well as the perspective of value added service providers. Selected service model should have a clear relative advantage over the existing way of operating and that the innovation complexity must be applicable from the aspect of customer. The most appropriate logistical service model should be based on building the additional services in the earlier phase of a customer demand chain (prior to transportation service). More specifically, the appropriate value should be offered for the firms other than in the last stage of the demand chain (purchasing of transportation service). The main customer characteristics should be considered. Cluster related industry should be analysed and the way production has been organized. Industries with a high amount of warehousing and transportation between non-value adding production phases can be considered as a target market for new services (Soinio et al., 2012).

Since CluCS promotes the establishment of a collaborative network of actors the value chain concept

can be considered. Value chain analysis can be used for identifying the potential for extra value creation. The value chain of the established network of actors is composed from individual value chains of each actor (manufacturers, 3PLs, terminals, transport operators, etc.). Establishment of a CluCS system will lead to improvements in value chain of each actor, potential cost advantages and also potential added values for manufacturers (lower costs or higher performance). For value added service providers the value chain model should identify the opportunities to provide improved service under the lower costs.

From the aspect of manufacturers, CluCS will certainly contribute to more intensive outsourcing of their logistics tasks (besides the core services like transportation and warehousing) since the system will bring a clear advantage to value added service providers through offering the service at a lower costs and with higher quality from the aspect of reliability, flexibility and responsiveness.

The focus of Cluster manager should be on supporting deeper specialization in VALS provider core activities and the potential for developing strategic VALS provider – manufacturer collaboration which will also motivate and enable outsourcing of advanced functions beyond common transport and warehousing services. Also, VALS can be considered as a part of relationship building between providers and manufacturers. The aim should be to establish strategic, long contracts since they provide income security and risk reduced. Also, the manufacturers have a diversity of logistics competences. Big manufacturers have in-house logistics departments, SMEs may have only purchasing sectors to control costs. Crucial questions are to align the value cases of these actors in the sense which VALSs a specific firm needs and how the costs of IT systems integration will be shared. Of course, economy of scale makes rate for particular service provision much cheaper. This supports the main criterion for VALS offering profitability, if the service is not profitable it will not be offered to a customer.

The role of Cluster manager in this case is very important. Cluster manager should build a network based on a dynamic interplay between contractual and relational governance, which in concrete case of VALS providers and shippers means that they are getting to know each other (contractual governance) and gradually understand possible synergies, operation capabilities and develop trust (relational governance). The analysis of the most frequently outsourced activities should be performed. The focus should be on supporting those strategic, IT-intensive and customer-facing instead of transactional, operational and repetitive.

2.3 Framework for engagement of stakeholders in CluCS network

The framework for transition from the current situation within the Cluster to a new collaborative ICT supported network contains three dimensions (Figure 2-1):

- The general system context;
- The governance model of the CluCS network;
- Cooperation dynamics and actions.

The system context – logistics cluster environment - generates opportunities and constraints – drivers and barriers - and influences the dynamics of the relationships between the stakeholders in the developed collaborative network. The proposed governance network is initiated and evolves within the general system context which represents the host of all legal, environmental and other influences that affect or they are affected by the governance model in the Cluster. The governance model is under the influence of the system context but also affects the system through the impact of its collaborative actions. The dynamics and performances of the governance model will be under the influence of external conditions by opening up new possibilities (expanding the governance network, covering broader market area in the Cluster) or generating new anticipated challenges (fluctuations in demand/supply conditions, technology related impacts).

Figure 1 Transition mechanism toward the target governance model/state (Smart-Rail, 2017)

Besides the contextual drivers (already explained in first part of this report) we have to emphasize the main motives – essential drivers for participating in this CluCS collaborative network:

- Presence of an orchestrator – Cluster manager in position to coordinate all activities within the established network.
- Drivers for cooperative action – Consider the already existing problems elaborated in the previous tasks – need for improved coordination of the actors within the Cluster – one of the most important, resource needs and interests (financial performances, economy of scope, scale, density), external threats/opportunities (technological breakthroughs of driverless trucks/legal framework that supports the development of intermodality).
- Interdependence – individual actors (shippers, LSPs, terminal operators etc.) are unable to cope with existing issues in transport and logistics;
- Uncertainty – uncertainty present in everyday business of LSPs, railway and terminal operators can drive them to cooperate in order to reduce, diffuse and share risk.

As it was mentioned, the proposed governance model is in essence a dynamic, hierarchical, distributed, cooperative decision making framework shaped by the drivers and barriers that emerge from the system context.

However, the implementation of the model and the degree to which it is effective is affected over time by two components:

- Dynamics of cooperation;
- Cooperative actions.

The dynamic nature of the model is generated by the essential drivers which encourage potential partners by the reduced transaction costs of collective actions and the actions that they produce over time.

The dynamics of cooperation can be viewed as an iterative interaction of three components – cooperative engagement, shared motivation and capacity building:

- 1) Cooperative engagement of stakeholders with different goals to solve problems and create value – Important for the cooperative network is to define who the partners are. Involving the “right” stakeholders is of crucial importance for successful establishing and longevity of the cooperative governance network. Good strategy which gains maximum synergy effects must be chosen for selecting the potential stakeholders in all cases (depending on the Cluster) when a choice exists. Besides the forming of the network, engagement of stakeholders involves the following iterative processes:
 - Evaluating the individual interests of every stakeholder – manufacturers, VALS provider, transport and terminal operators;

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- Continuous effort to build shared meaning by articulating the common purpose and objectives, clarifying tasks and expectations;
- Examination of issues and different perspectives of stakeholders involved;
- Alignment of different interests and conflict resolution.

All these processes of cooperative engagement of stakeholders contribute to mutual understanding of stakeholders. These iterative processes create and reinforce shared motivation and build the capacity for joint action.

- 2) Shared motivation consists from mutual trust, understanding, internal legitimacy and commitment. When a trustworthy and credible cooperation network is formed, with compatible and interdependent interests, this legitimizes and motivates ongoing cooperation. Trust and reciprocity guide the interactions between the stakeholders and further reinforce confidence in legitimacy and efficacy of the cooperative dynamics. This leads to creating bonds of shared commitment which enable participants to cross the boundaries that previously separated them and to focus on a shared path.

The purpose of the establishing CluCS network is to generate the desired improvements for the Cluster that could not be accomplished separately. On this way the capacity of the Cluster in whole is enhanced as well as the capacity of individual stakeholders to achieve the common purpose.

- 3) Capacity building is specified during the establishing a cooperative network and further actions within the stakeholder engagement process and it is based on motivations of all stakeholders regarding their cooperative purpose. It will be for sure adjusted to the scope and scale of the objectives and activities of the whole cooperative network.

The capacity is also dynamic, it can be viewed as the outcome of interacting cycles of engagement of stakeholders and shared motivation. With the developing of capacity, the engagement of stakeholders and the shared motivation will also be improved. In synergy this leads to more effective actions and impacts of the network.

- 3.1) Procedural arrangements represent operating rules which will be established by the intermediary – Cluster Manager and it will be clearly defined by formal and informal contracts. Also procedural arrangements must be defined at the intra-organizational level – how each individual actor will manage itself in cooperative relationship. It is important that actors have more fluid and complex internal authority structure.
- 3.2) Leadership has already been stated as an essential driver for cooperation. It represents very important factor of cooperative governance network. In the case of suggested governance model Cluster Manager has leadership role as a facilitator of information sharing and orchestrator of the network.
- 3.3) Knowledge in the capacity for joint action represents a currency for collaboration. Considering that the model is dynamic and continuously improving the knowledge must be shared among the stakeholders. Cluster manager provides information sharing platform for sharing quantifiable and live information about transport flows. This also affects cooperative efficiency of the network.
- 3.4) One benefit of cooperation is the potential for sharing and leveraging scarce resources. Resources useful for establishing and governing proposed relationship include funding (as a support for establishing information sharing infrastructure), technical and logistical support and skills for implementation of IT infrastructure. Through the cooperative dynamics all resource incompatibilities can be leveraged and redistributed as shared resources to lead to common goals of the cooperative governance model.

The purpose of this framework is to initiate actions that could not have been performed by any of the stakeholders in Cluster acting alone. **Cooperative actions** represent the essence of the cooperative governance model. They result from the strategy developed during the cooperative dynamics and represent the efforts aimed to achieve the objectives of the governance model. **Impacts** result from the actions and represent changes of state within the system context. These changes are reflection (desirable to be as much as possible) of all the drivers stated as well as the general objectives of Clusters 2.0 project. The most important impact should be higher market share of logistics cluster generated intermodal transport. Impacts may be considered as the added value of this innovation resulted from cooperative actions. These impacts have their physical dimension – volume of freight flows shifted from road to rail, environmental dimension – lower CO₂ emissions, social dimension –

lower social costs of transport system, economic dimension – savings in capital and operational costs (investments in transport infrastructure, higher productivity of mobile capacities) and political dimension – satisfying the aims of European transport policy. By the nature these effects are cumulative and with longer term impacts.

The proposed cooperative governance model must contain **adaptive feature**. This may occur as a result of changes in the system context (changes in drivers for example) or directly in response to the perceived fulfilling the objectives. This feedback mechanism will be based on permanent monitoring of defined KPIs and it will represent “returns” to partners in network to justify their involvement efforts. If the cooperative network does not produce the impacts which are close to the identified objectives governance model should be adjusted – targets, actions cooperative dynamics and investments should be modified.

3 Analysis of actors’ needs [Leader: ZLC; Partners: IBI]

CluCS represents and IT platform aimed to establish coordination and collaboration between terminals on the one side and pooling cargo coordinated processes on the other side (Deliverable D2.3). The Cluster Community System (CluCS) supports the governance of the Proximity Terminal Network (PTN) and Cluster operations through efficient management of the information related to cargo flows and assets within the nodes of the Cluster. Thus, the CluCS should optimize the functioning of the PTN within the Cluster and enhance efficiency and competitiveness for all involved logistics actors operating in the region.

The CluCS concept needs very intensive and efficient cooperation between all involved stakeholders. However, interests of stakeholders are not fully aligned because their “environments” are not identical. Further, for such a complex innovation like the CluCS concept is, it is important that all decision makers adopt the innovation. This adoption is known as collective action and it can be obtained when the value created for each stakeholder, or potential losses of values are balanced (Smart Rail, 2016).

In order to align the value cases of the most important stakeholders in the CluCS network it will be applied the Value Case Methodology (VCM). Involvement of manufacturers and VALS providers will depend on the success of established CluCS network.

In general, the first step of the VCM is to identify the main stakeholders and their specific roles during design, implementation and uptake of the CluCS solution (Figure 2-1). Then, after analyzing the current situation, priorities and preferences for each stakeholder will be aggregated and the solution will be fine-tuned. An important part in the value case methodology is that it creates transparency in the distribution of effects of the expected innovation. Here, it should be noted that some of the effects could be positive for one stakeholder (and will be ‘drivers’), while the same effects might be negative for the other (barriers). Based on this analysis (business and policy) interventions or measures can be derived, which are required to overcome barriers, while exploiting the drivers.

Figure 2 An illustration of the Value Case Methodology (Dittrich and Dijk, 2015)

There are four main steps for properly conducting the VCM:

- The value case analysis, describing the main drivers, barriers and values for each stakeholder;
- The value quantification analysis, for determining the values as well as their sources, units, clear description, etc.;
- The value sensitivity analysis, where sensitivity analysis is performed on the different parameters and
- The value alignment analysis, where agreement is expected to be reached on the solution elements.

3.1 Value Case Analysis

3.1.1 Interests and Values delivered by stakeholders

An important part in the value case methodology is to create transparency in the distribution of effects of the foreseen innovation for the actors within the network. While some of the effects will be positive for one stakeholder (drivers) the same effects might be negative for the other (barriers). Based on this analysis interventions or measures can be derived, which are required to overcome barriers, while exploiting drivers.

For this purpose, stakeholder analysis was conducted. The analysis regards stakeholders' perspectives, barriers, demands and preferences for implementing and utilizing CluCS concept which will improve the coordination and collaboration between actors in the logistics cluster. The analysis is based on a stakeholders' survey conducted on 12th June 2019 in Interporto Bologna, during CluCS presentation event, in order to collect all necessary information that characterizes the current situation, motives and barriers for stakeholders to use the IT platform for intermodal service booking, cargo consolidation and cargo pooling. The main stakeholders (Cluster community manager, shippers, terminal operators, railway operators and LSPs - among them VALS providers) affected by CluCS innovation were included in the analysis.

The interests and values delivered are summarized in Tables 1-5 below.

Table 1 Rule, interest and CluCS value delivered to Shippers

Stakeholder
Shippers
Role
Main users of the CluCS services
Supplying volumes to the transport chain

Interest	Value Delivered
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability • Visibility • Cost • Shorter lead times • Higher profitability & competitiveness • More efficient transport chains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved market position • Improved supply chain visibility which leads to better operations planning • Enhanced capacity for facing unexpected events at PTN level; • Available information regarding offered logistics services (terminals and LSPs); • Intermodal service booking capability; • Optimized logistics solutions (cost/time) through cargo consolidation and cargo pooling.

Table 2 Role, interest and CluCS value delivered to Terminal Operators

Stakeholder	
Terminal Operator	
Role	
Responsible for safe and efficient delivery and packing up of goods on ships, truck and trains. In case of railway, terminal operator performs assembly, dismantling and loading/unloading of trains.	
Interest	Value Delivered
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work process optimisation through improved scheduling of activities • Higher productivity and capacity • Higher profitability & competitiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced visibility and reliability • Improved coordination of activities • Less dwell times • Proactive decision making

Table 3 Role, interest and CluCS value delivered to Railway Operator

Stakeholder	
Railway Operator	
Role	
Performs intra-cluster and inter-cluster railway transport	
Interest	Value Delivered
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved modal share • Higher profit • Enhanced utilization of railway assets and crews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced reliability & visibility & flexibility • Enhanced customer satisfaction • Enhanced volume through cargo consolidation

Table 4 Role, interest and CluCS value delivered to LSP

Stakeholder	
LSP	
Role	
Arrange full load, door-to-door transportation by selecting and combining without prejudice the most sustainable and efficient mode of transportation. 3PL provides its own vehicles, 4PL acts as integrators.	
Interest	Value Delivered

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better market position • Profitability • Customer satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cargo consolidations/cargo pooling – involvement of rail legs which will provide more combinations and therefore more flexibility for LSPs • Easier market access through intermodal services booking functionality • Enhanced visibility and reliability of services
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Table 5 Role, interest and value delivered to VALS provider

Stakeholder	
VALS provider	
Role	
Provide value-added logistics services	
Interest	Value Delivered
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer satisfaction • Profit • Competitiveness • Proactive decision making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased interaction of stakeholders with VALS providers; • More, quicker and cost effective realised services and higher capacities; • Enhanced coordination among the actors; which leads to provision of improved VALSs; • Reduced logistics costs; • Last mile optimization.

Table 6 Role, interest and value delivered to PTN Manager

Stakeholder	
PTN Manager	
Role	
Neutral third party (Interporto Bologna) whose main function is to provide shippers and LSPs with optimisation suggestions based on the data provided by the CluCS	
Interest	Value Delivered
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitiveness of the Cluster and own competitiveness • Improved decision making operational/tactical/strategic level • Higher profitability through seamless operations and higher productivity within the Cluster and PTN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved coordination between stakeholders in the Cluster/PTN network • Enhanced planning through provided inputs for cargo consolidation/cargo pooling • Improved supply chain visibility

3.1.2 Assessment of barriers and drivers

Established CluCS network will result in a change of business for the different stakeholders. For realizing the future situation there will be different drivers and barriers for each stakeholder. Next table contains the drivers and barriers for all stakeholders involved in CluCS innovation.

Table 7 Barriers and drivers of involved stakeholders

Stakeholder	Change in Business	Drivers	Barriers
Shippers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No change in business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased running capital costs • Improved carbon footprint • Better predictability of business process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of IT systems

Stakeholder	Change in Business	Drivers	Barriers
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost savings due to cargo consolidation and cargo pooling 	
Terminal Operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core business remains the same • Supply Chain Orientation since the terminal also acts as a part of the network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market position improved • Productivity/capacity improved • Costs decreased • Profit increased 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process redesign • Supply chain orientation • Unwillingness for information sharing issue
Railway Operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business process redesign due to more visible planning of operations and more intensive communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved market position • Improved assets/crews productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply chain orientation • Unwillingness to share information • IT systems integration
LSPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core business remains the same • Network integration implies business process redesign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved competitiveness • Customer satisfaction • Profit • Costs reduced due to more flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT systems integration • Supply Chain Orientation • Business process redesign
Value added service providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due to the improved coordination among the actors in supply chain VALS providers will be able to provide improved supply chain solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating more business resulting in increased profit • Competitiveness • Customer satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT systems integration • Information sharing • Eventual costs of buying external services
PTN Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud-based collaborative business model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profitability • Cluster's competitiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT systems integration • Costs of service provision

Focusing only on shippers and VALS providers, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Shippers expect better business results due to decreased service costs, and also more visible, flexible and reliable service. As the main users of the CluCS platform services shippers benefit from the possibility to book intermodal logistic services departing from the cluster and with destination both intra and extra cluster. Through cargo consolidation and cargo pooling transport capacities are better utilized, lead times are decreased and transport costs reduced.
- VALS providers expect more intensive engagement in the intra- and inter- cluster related transport and logistics activities as a result of more intensive transportation and warehousing services. CluCS enables value added services thanks to the dynamic network: more, quicker and cost effective realized services and higher capacities. CluCS may play a facilitator role that enhances the development of collaboration practices and value-added services between co-located firms.
- On the other side, the cost of participation to the CluCS network is also a barrier for these stakeholders due to their unwillingness to cooperate in this more intensive information sharing

concept, and also due to high investments in IT infrastructure that will enable the participation of some actors in the concept (like shippers and VALS providers are).

Based on conducted stakeholder analysis, the value network map that represents relationships among the value chain actors has been designed. Together with these relationships, VNA (Value Network Map) enables displaying resources that actors exchange or pool as part of their operations (information, mobile capacities, infrastructure and financial assets). Information on exchange resources among actors is qualitative – the map illustrates that two actors exchange money and information but not the exact quantity of those two. However, these key resources are of strategic type and they are considered as underlying valuable resources achieved from the relationship among the stakeholders within the CluCS solution. Therefore, the final output of VNA is the value network map that looks like on the following figure. Only the main stakeholders in Cluster which are empowered to initiate this innovation are considered. The whole network includes also rail infrastructure managers, wagon keepers, shunting operators, and related ministries.

Types of influences:

- I = Information flow
- TS = Train service
- TsS= Transshipment service
- TWS = Transportation-warehousing service
- VALS = Value added logistics service

Figure 2 Value network map

3.2 Value quantification analysis

All the effects that express motives and barriers of stakeholders based on stakeholders’ survey are summarized in previous section. However, these potential changes that stakeholders expect from CluCS concept are qualitatively expressed. Qualitative effects are often analyzed by quantifying the effect. In the literature, among many other techniques, multi-criteria analysis (MCA) and conjoint analysis (CA) are the most frequently used quantification techniques.

For purpose of value quantification analysis in the context of CluCS innovation MCA is chosen as the more appropriate method. With the MCA partners involved in T2.5 assign weights to effects. With this input, MCA provides an overview of how different effects combine to a positive or negative outcome for the stakeholders.

AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) is a multi-criteria decision making method introduced by Thomas A.

Clusters 2.0

Saaty (Satty, 1980). AHP uses a multi-level hierarchical structure of objectives, criteria, and alternatives. On the base of pairwise comparisons (of elements on lower level against the elements on upper level – criteria against objective, alternatives against criteria) it is possible to derive the weights of importance of the criteria, and relative importance of alternatives against each individual criterion. Main steps of AHP are:

- 1) Problem is decomposed into a hierarchy of goal, criteria and alternatives;
- 2) Data are collected from DMs in the pairwise comparison matrices;
- 3) The principal eigen value as well as the corresponding right eigenvector of the comparison matrix give the relative importance of the various criteria being compared;
- 4) The consistency of each pairwise comparison matrix is evaluated;
- 5) Each alternative´ rate is multiplied by weight on upper levels and aggregated in order to obtain the local ratings with respect to each criterion.

The details of the method will be demonstrated through its implementation in case of VCM. In this application, the goal is to evaluate the effects each stakeholder expects from participating in a CluCS concept. Based on these preferences – preferred conjoint features of an innovation (CT – Computer Tomography concept in this case) it is possible to offer a concept which will satisfy interests of all stakeholders. Based on previous step of VCM we can summarize the set of all values that stakeholders and experts associate with CT innovation:

- 1) Profit;
- 2) Capacity utilization;
- 3) Reliability of service;
- 4) Flexibility of service;
- 5) Visibility of service;
- 6) Cost of IT system integration;
- 7) Cost of service provision;
- 8) Mental shift (for example, unwillingness for information sharing);
- 9) Lead time.

Five pairwise comparison matrices (for each stakeholder one matrix that expresses its relative preference) which have to be fulfilled by all actors involved in this analysis represent matrices of corresponding dimension (dependent on the number of attributes that each stakeholder connects with CT concept) with 1s on main diagonal. Only the part above the main diagonal needs to be filled because the part below represents reciprocal values of the upper part. Experts for each row *i*, column *j* pair of elements (*i*, *j*), in each (*i*, *j*) cell put their own preference regarding the relative importance of *i* against *j*. Preferences are based on a scale, called Saaty’s scale presented in Table 8.

Table 8 Saaty’s scale

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective
3	Weak importance of one over another	Experience and judgment slightly favor one activity over another
5	Essential or strong importance	Experience and judgment strong favour one activity over another
7	Demonstrated importance	An activity is strongly favored and its dominance demonstrated in practice
9	Absolute importance	The evidence favouring one activity over another is over highest possible order of affirmation

2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values between the two adjacent judgments	When compromise is needed
Reciprocals of above nonzero	If activity i have none of the above nonzero numbers assigned to it when compared with activity j, then j has reciprocal value when compared with i.	

During the matrix fulfilling it is very important to be consistent. Inconsistency appears in cases such as for example situation where the effect i is strongly favored than j, and j is slightly favored than k, and k is slightly favored than i. In these situations, the reliability of results decreases. In order to cope with inconsistency, AHP uses consistency ratio CR which must be below 0.1. If CR is higher than 0.1 that means that expert or a group of experts was not consistent during the matrix fulfilling process and the whole procedure must be repeated.

Stakeholders and experts filled seven comparison matrices which comprise preferences of each of the seven stakeholders involved in the transportation planning process of rail enabled CT solution. However, it would be needed to know the relative impact (considering the value it delivers, role and “share” in whole process) of every stakeholder in the value network. This is important when the relative contribution of every effect to the CluCS concept is analyzed. Next figure shows the structure of the model.

Figure 3 Structure of the model

Stakeholders are ranked according to their impact (the value they deliver to the CluCS concept). Pairwise comparison matrices with respect to goal – CluCS concept are as in Table 9:

Table 9 Impact of stakeholders in rail enabled CluCS concept – Pairwise comparison matrix

	PTN Manager	Railway Operator	Shipper	Terminal operator
LSP/VALS	½	2	½	2
PTN Manager		2	½	2
Railway Operator			1/3	½
Shipper				2

As it is previously stated, pairwise comparison matrices are filled with relative preferences expressed on a scale from 1-9 (Table 3-2). For example, considering the value it delivers to the CluCS concept, LSP/VALS is slightly more preferred than Terminal operator (value 2 assigned). On the other side, Shipper is a much more preferred than Railway Operator (value 3 assigned). The final rank of stakeholders in CluCS is given on following figure.

Figure 4 Relative rank of stakeholders in CluCS concept according to the value they deliver to it (CI=0.03)

Relative priority of effects from the aspect of each stakeholder is presented in following part of this section. These are quantitative expressions or part worth utilities related to stakeholder's value perceptions given in previous section.

In case of CluCS concept (according to Table 1 and also insights from Stakeholders survey) Shippers expect better business results due to decreased service costs, and also more visible service (Figure 5). Decreased service costs will be achieved due to cargo consolidation and cargo pooling, as well as more intensive shift to rail/intermodal. CluCS will provide required visibility and reliability on Cluster & PTN level. Certain level of flexibility in terms of possibility to change schedules will be possible since the LSPs will have additional transport mode to consider as a competitive option. Therefore, five of nine attributes are related to Shippers. All these attributes with their attribute levels (these small variations are needed for determining the point sensitivity of stakeholders) are represented on Figure 5.

Figure 5 Attributes related to Shipper

Pairwise comparison matrices filled by the experts and stakeholders and rank of all attribute levels look as follows (Table 10).

Table 10 Pairwise comparison matrix for determining the part worth utilities of attribute levels

Profit	Low (loss)	Medium (break even)	High (>break even)	Utility (CI=0.008)	Lead Time	Low (delay >=24h)	Average (delay <=24h)	High (on time)	Utility (CI=0.008)
Low	1	1/2	1/3	0.1634	Low	1	1/2	1/3	0.1634
Medium		1	1/2	0.2969	Average		1	1/2	0.2969
High			1	0.5396	High			1	0.5396
Visibility	No visibility	Partial visibility	Full visibility	Utility (CI=0.07)	Reliability	Low (Delay out of the time window)	Medium (Delay, but within the time window)	High (on time)	Utility (CI=0.03)
No visibility	1	1/3	1/4	0.1172	Low	1	1/3	1/5	0.1047
Partial visibility		1	1/3	0.2684	Medium		1	1/3	0.2582
Full visibility			1	0.6144	High			1	0.6369
Flexibility	No flexibility	Medium flexibility	High flexibility (fully conforming to required modification)	Utility (CI=0.07)					
No flexibility	1	1/3	1/4	0.1172					
Medium flexibility		1	1/3	0.2683					
High flexibility			1	0.6144					

Pairwise comparison matrix for Shipper' related attributes has the following content (Table 11).

Table 11 Pairwise comparison matrix for attribute utilities of Shipper

	Lead Time	Profit	Reliability	Visibility	Rank (CI=0.04)
Flexibility	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	0.106
Lead Time		1/2	2	2	0.245
Profit			2	2	0.329
Reliability				1/2	0.140

Figure 7 contains graphical interpretation of preferences or utilities allocated to the attributes related to Shipper. Shippers expect better business results due to decreased service costs (through increased productivity based on cargo pooling and cargo consolidation) and improved transport chain coordination which results in higher reliability and shorter lead time and more visible service (Figure 7). Certain level of flexibility in terms of possibility to change schedules, lengths, freight, wagons will also be attained by possibility for proactive decision making and having available other transport options than road. The size of the costs of IT system integration will depend on whether the shipper is a big manufacturer with its own proprietary systems or a SME which, in this case, may represent an important barrier to join CluCS network. This cost may also include the cost of participation of shipper in CluCS.

Figure 6 Relative rank of effects from the aspect of the Shipper

The relative priority of attributes considered as the most important for LSP/VALS providers is presented on Figure 8. LSP/VALSs is interested for seven of nine attributes in total. Higher level of coordination in Cluster and PTN should lead to higher level of competitiveness for Cluster in general, and also for LSPs/VALS providers. Synchronized operation of transport and logistics services at Cluster level, will improve responsiveness and decrease delays and waiting times at nodes as well as generate enough volumes to implement fully efficient intermodal transport connections from Cluster's hubs to external destinations. Increased satisfaction of clients is expected also (shippers/manufacturers) through higher level of visibility, flexibility and reliability. Capacity utilization will be attained by cargo pooling and cargo consolidation. On the other side, LSP/VALS providers consider some cost of service provision which in case of LSPs could be related to business process redesign and more intensive SCO whereas in case of VALS providers potential costs may arise from buying external services in order to satisfy client requests or engagement additional knowledge and time for provision of additional services. Cost of IT system integration which must be considered in case of LSPs/VALS providers needs to be minimized and clearly outweighed by CluCS tangible benefits. In case of LSPs/VALS providers, CluCS will facilitate main services (transportation and warehousing) and support provision of value-added services. Cost of IT integration may also include a cost of participation of LSP/VALS in CluCS.

Figure 7 Relative rank of the effects from the aspect of the LSP/VALS provider

Relative utilities related to Railway operators reflect their tendency to increase modal share and utilization of capacities (Figure 9). On the other side, some cost related to improvements of information sharing capacities must be taken into account. Mental shift includes unwillingness for higher level of information sharing and also represent a value that has to be taken into account from the aspect of Railway Operator.

Figure 8 Utility values for Railway Operator

CluCS facilitates aggregation of terminal networks to better organize intermodal flows. Through process optimization and significantly improved coordination terminal operators will substantially improve reliability (Figure 10). Visibility will act as a supporting utility to the first one. Higher level of utilization of available capacities (through increased productivity, minimized dwell times in terminals) will be achieved. However, they also take into account the cost of IT system integration, which should be outbalanced by profit expected from higher volume of handling and efficiency of operations in terminal.

Figure 9 Utility values for Terminal Operator

PTN Manager (in the context of LL2 also PTN manager is also the main terminal) should act as a neutral orchestrator that coordinates the PTN aiming for an optimal utilization of resources and assets within the terminals by which it is formed. The main function of PTN manager is to provide shippers and LSPs with optimization suggestions in base of the data provided by CluCS. Cargo consolidation (based on information provided by CluCS) between points united by rail services should be promoted by the Cluster Community Manager in order to follow the Clusters 2.0 main guidelines. Cargo pooling opportunities among shippers that have expressed (published in the platform) their will to “bundle” sub optimal recurring cargo flows should be encouraged and sponsored by the Cluster Community Manager. PTN Manager expects some benefit from orchestration activity (directly through service fees and indirectly through increased flows in main terminal of PTN). On the other hand, PTN Manager should account for costs of service provision related to trained personnel to perform the service. Cost of IT system integration represents also one of important utilities for PTN Manager.

Figure 10 Utility values for PTN Manager

Now, after evaluating the hierarchy it is possible to determine the absolute utilities of all effects or attributes which are expected by the stakeholders. These utilities are calculated by multiplying all relative weights along the path from the top level objective to the level of attribute (Figure 12). As it can be seen, the overall aim of the concept is a contribution to better business results. Visibility also represents one of the utilities that most of stakeholders expect. Cost of participation play also a large share at some stakeholders, due to their unwillingness to cooperate in this more intensive information sharing concept, and also due to high investments in IT infrastructure that will enable the participation of some actors in the concept (like LSPs are).

Figure 11 Absolute utilities of all effects expected by the stakeholders

However, considering that the focus is to find preferred conjoint features of CluCS concept (the best combination of features) it is needed to focus on partial utilities of all attribute levels in order to be able to evaluate rail enabled CT concept with different pre specified levels of key attributes. Part worth utilities are computed by multiplying the absolute utility of an attribute and a relative utility value of certain level belonging to that attribute (Figure 13). This is done for every DM (stakeholder) individually.

Figure 12 Part worth utilities per stakeholder

3.3 Value sensitivity

The aim of this section is to demonstrate the sensitivity of each stakeholder to a change in the value of every attribute, so called point sensitivity [2]. By generating various versions of CluCS concept (by varying the attribute levels) and by their quantification it is possible to realize the incremental effect of each attribute level upon the CluCS concept choice. In other words, the idea is to present how much should stakeholder's utility perception change when the proposal changes. Stakeholder's utility in case of rail enabled CT solution can be viewed as the willingness to participate in the solution.

It is also useful to define the threshold value, or in other words, the attribute value which will still generate some utility acceptable to the stakeholder. Every level of attribute which is lower by utility than a threshold value will be rejected by the stakeholder. Threshold value for each stakeholder is assumed to correspond to a medium level of an attribute value.

All levels of attributes and their meaning are presented in following table.

Table 12 Levels of attributes

	Attribute level		
	Low	Medium	High
LSP/VALS provider			
Flexibility	no flexibility, changes/modifications not possible	not fully conforming to required modification	fully conforming to required modification

	(measurement for elasticity)		
Profit	= < production cost	= break even	= > break even
Reliability	Delay – out of specified time window	Delay – within the specified time window	On time
Visibility	no visibility	visibility only partial or only per demand	full visibility automatically
Cost of service provision	Zero, without charge	0.1% of expected turnover	0.5% of expected turnover
Cost of IT system integration	Zero, without charge	0.1% of expected turnover	0.5% of expected turnover
Railway operator			
Profit	= < production cost	= break even	= > break even
Capacity utilization	70%-80% of available capacity	40%-70% of available capacity	10%-30% of available capacity
Cost of IT system integration	Zero, without charge	0.1% of expected turnover	0.5% of expected turnover
Mental Shift	no willingness to share data	only upon request according to contracted process	actively contributing
Shipper			
Lead time	delay \geq 24 hours	delay, but \leq 24 hours	on time
Profit	loss	break even	= > break even
Visibility	no visibility	visibility only partial or only per demand	full visibility automatically
Reliability	Delay – out of specified time window	Delay – within the specified time window	On time
Flexibility	no flexibility, changes/modifications not possible (measurement for elasticity)	not fully conforming to required modification	fully conforming to required modification
Cost of IT system integration	Zero, without charge	0.1% of expected turnover	0.5% of expected turnover
PTN Manager			
Profit	loss	break even	= > break even
Visibility	no visibility	visibility only partial or only per demand	full visibility automatically
Cost of IT system integration	Zero, without charge	0.1% of expected turnover	0.5% of expected turnover
Cost of service provision	Zero, without charge	0.1% of expected turnover	0.5% of expected turnover
Terminal operator			
Capacity utilization	70%-80% of available capacity	40%-70% of available capacity	10%-30% of available capacity
Reliability	refusal of acceptance due to congestion	immoderate waiting time	access and handling without delay
Visibility	no visibility	visibility only partial or only per demand	full visibility automatically
Cost of service provision	Zero, without charge	0,1% of handling fee	0.5% of handling fee
Profit	loss	break even	= > break even

It is needed to demonstrate sensitivity of stakeholder to a small change as compared to an attribute value of the idea behind CluCS concept. This idea is based on providing a concept which will enable

shippers and LSPs/VALS intermodal service proposals characterized with improved service and decreased cost.

The idea is to present how much should stakeholder's utility perception change when the proposal changes. Stakeholder's utility in case of CluCS solution can be viewed as the willingness to participate in the solution.

In order to collaborate shipper will expect substantial improvement of some key attributes, higher profit due to lower expenses by cargo pooling and cargo consolidation and also including railway legs and due to shorter lead time and full visibility of the transport chain. Shippers also insist on higher reliability and flexibility attributes which are not very bright feature of railway transport. Figure 14 represents the results of sensitivity analysis for Shipper. With increasing the attribute value the perception of Shipper's utility increases. Yellow colored points with associated utility values represent assumed thresholds for accepting the innovation by the stakeholder.

Figure 13 Sensitivity analysis - Shipper

The same situation regarding the sensitivity analysis holds for VALS providers (Figure 15). With increasing the level of coordination, visibility and decreasing the costs of service provision and IT system integration the utility value of VALS provider raises. Cost related attributes have negative sensitivity in the sense that an increase in the outcome of that value means that the stakeholder is unhappy about this increase.

Figure 14 Sensitivity analysis – LSP/VALS provider

Profit also represents one of the main expectations of Railway Operators (Figure 16). CluCS aims to find rail idle capacity (empty wagons) and tries to match it with road cargo flows destinations reachable by train. Therefore, high cargo utilization is also expected by Railway Operators. However, they are afraid of high cost of IT system integration which includes high investments in IT infrastructure. So, for them, in order to join to the CluCS network, a solution which does not include so much of investments would be the best option. As all players from railway field in Europe, ROs also must cope with mental shift in order to increase the value of their service.

Figure 15 Sensitivity analysis – Railway Operator

Joining the CluCS network should bring a certain financial effect to Terminal operators. On the other side they must count on a certain cost of IT system integration which includes also a service fee for provision of CluCS service by PTN Manager. CluCS can function as a tool to identify cases of potential cargo consolidation and cargo pooling and coordinate these processes. Terminals within the Cluster and PTN can act as service providers in charge of the activity of cargo pooling and cargo consolidation. Also, by improved coordination in the terminal utilization of terminal capacity will be increased. Terminal operators give the same utility values to visibility and reliability attributes (Figure 17).

Figure 16 Sensitivity analysis – Terminal Operator

PTN Manager coordinates the whole network by analyzing optimization potentialities detected by CluCS and makes proposals for optimized logistics solutions to shippers and different stakeholders involved in the transport chain. PTN Manager expects some profit for this service, and he also may count on some costs for service provision. High visibility as one of the main prerequisites for efficient service provision represents one of expected attributes.

Figure 17 Sensitivity analysis – PTN Manager

3.4 Value alignment

Sensitivity analysis may provide an insight in the attributes which may serve for value compensation among stakeholders. Compensation must be with minimal costs and maximal effect. For example, alignment on the value like “Cost of participation” will affect most of the stakeholders in CluCS concept. Therefore, in this case, we select the collective effects for alignment analysis.

For example, only Railway Operator considers Mental Shift whereas an alignment on the value like “Cost of IT system integration” is likely to affect all the stakeholders in CluCS concept. Therefore, in this case, we select the collective effects for alignment analysis.

These effects and stakeholders that benefit from them are:

- Profit – LSP/VALS, PTN Manager, Shipper, Railway Operator, Terminal Operator;
- Cost of IT system integration – LSP/VALS, PTN Manager, Shipper, Railway Operator, Terminal Operator;
- Visibility – LSP/VALS, Shipper, PTN Manager, Terminal Operator;
- Capacity utilization – LSP/VALS, Railway Operator, Terminal Operator;
- Reliability – LSP/VALS, Shipper, Terminal Operator.

Graphs from previous section (analysis by stakeholder) as well as the graphs presented here may give an insight about which attribute has a large effect on the acceptance of stakeholders. Therefore, it is needed to realize how much compensation – alignment is needed. Alignment represents needed level of increase or decrease of an attribute value which is offered by the initial design of proposed innovation – CluCS concept in this case in order to reach acceptance by the actors to engage in CluCS concept. Some stakeholders would need compensation whereas some other can compensate if that is needed. Considering the importance and the effects of CluCS concept there are no blockers to this innovation so it will not be difficult to propose redistribution of values in case of possible misalignments identified.

If we look in attribute “Profit” we can see that all stakeholders show positive point elasticity and their threshold utility values (yellow colored points corresponding to ordinate value) are assumed to correspond to medium level of attribute value offered by the CluCS concept. This is reasonable assumption since it is expected that CluCS concept contributes to a significant increase of efficiency of freight flows within the Cluster and PTN. PTN Manager will probably gain more than only to cover the cost of service provision and other stakeholders will operate on a level higher than break even due to decreased operational costs or increased revenues from higher volume of work. Therefore, the medium level of attribute “Profit” is a minimum level which will be provided by the concept.

Figure 18 Point sensitivity curves of value “Profit”

Costs of IT service integration represent very important criteria for all stakeholders. For example, for shippers (large manufacturers as well as SMEs) and LSP/VALS providers the possibility of

compensation can be considered. The form of compensation can be only non-financial. Other partners can compensate VALS providers by granting them contracts for predominantly use of their services. This means increased volume of cargo flows for VALS providers and respectively increase of their financial profit. In open market conditions this will be hardly achieved but it is possible theoretically to be implemented.

Figure 19 Point sensitivity curves of value “Cost of IT service integration”

The same holds for attribute “Capacity utilization”. By the initial idea of CluCS it is expected to increase the level of capacity utilization on much higher level than it is a medium level which corresponds to threshold utility value of stakeholders.

Figure 20 Point sensitivity curves of value “Capacity utilization”

According to point sensitivity curves on Figure 22 it is obvious that the visibility is a very appreciated attribute by the PTN Manager (high sensitivity and threshold value) and Shipper also. Some lower perception is evident in case of LSP/VALS provider and Terminal Operator. Considering that one of the main features of CluCS concept is high level of visibility this will not represent the weak point in the sense of possible value misalignment.

Figure 21 Point sensitivity curves of value “Visibility”

3.5 Business options in CluCS context

CluCS concept requires different investments and services from each stakeholder, and the engagement of multiple stakeholders is essential to the successful implementation of the concept. It is of crucial importance to identify the cost and benefit positions for all stakeholders and to raise the awareness of these cases across the value network. With this knowledge and common understanding possible business options can be identified and analyzed to further define the innovation and its impact on the existing network of stakeholders. In general, according to the graphs presented it is obvious that all stakeholders will agree to cooperate in this innovation. However, there are possible critical points which have to be taken into account.

3.5.1 Scenarios for cost alignment

Considering the cost perspective of CluCS concept, from previous analysis may be concluded that possible weak points of this innovation lie in cost of IT system integration. As there are no precise estimations of attributes, some if-then scenarios for these attributes can be made.

As regards the cost of IT system integration, high level of this attribute will lead to unwillingness of stakeholders to participate. However, if one stakeholder has higher expenses due to IT system integration than financial benefits, taking into account the longer effects, he has to be compensated financially, otherwise he will not participate. Financial compensation might be on a bilateral contractual basis. For example, VALS provider gets extra fee from PTN manager for implementing IT solutions. On the other side, PTN manager can achieve improved utilization of resources and assets, cargo consolidation and pooling and can coordinate rail and maritime cargo consolidation on more efficient way and can ask higher prices from the shipper who will be able to earn the higher costs back from the market.

3.5.2 Scenarios for risk alignment

While all involved stakeholders are driven to achieve better business results and increased customer satisfaction, there are some individual and interacting barriers which are holding them back and imply a certain degree of risk. In order to assess risk and suggest some scenarios, benefit/risk relationships between stakeholders can be analyzed.

Again, in the context of AHP, the direction of comparison can be reversed and the expected benefits of stakeholders from the CluCS concept can be quantified. This quantification assumes a sum of stakeholder' utilities for all positive financial as well as non-financial effects (Figure 23).

Figure 22 Rank of stakeholders with respect to expected benefits

On the other side, the same ranking can be made regarding the risks of relying on CluCS. It is assumed that the intensity of risk for each stakeholder is proportional to the investments (financial and non-financial) into the innovation. Therefore, this estimation of risk is based on a summing of utilities for all negative financial as well as non-financial effects that stakeholders expect from CluCS concept (Figure 24).

Figure 23 Rank of stakeholders according to the risk associated

If it is found out that LSP/VALS providers, shippers or terminal operators see the high potential benefit from participation (benefit/risk ratio $\gg 1$), they will most probably be the motor of CluCS. Their motivation should be used to convince other stakeholders with a less than acceptable benefit/risk ratio to support the concept. The 'driver' has to invest manpower/time into the project during the initial phase in order to convince stakeholders to join the platform. According to the results of benefit/risk comparisons it can be said that all stakeholders are motivated in some way to take the risk to join CluCS platform.

4 Definition of CluCS interfaces with manufacturing and integration with value added services [Leader: IBI; Partners: NALLIAN]

Information technologies chosen for the development of CluCS has allowed the reproduction of the PTN / Cluster concept in a data network level: each supply chain actor of a regional or sovra-regional PTN could become a node using standard transport protocol and security policies.

Figure 24 Hierarchical collaborative distributed network of hyper connected clusters

Clusters has been established with an incremental approach. The first phase has consisted of publishing service catalog offered by LSPs with the aim to reach a wide audience of shippers, both in the local PTN and at Cluster level: shippers within the PTN and Cluster benefit from the possibility to book intermodal logistic services departing from the cluster and with destinations both intra and extra cluster. At the same time terminal operator and MTOs have found in CluCS an essential tool that allows them to fulfill their role as aggregator of cargo flows in view of optimizing intermodal transport by cargo consolidation and cargo pooling processes.

When shippers will start interacting with CluCS, the enlargement of the basis of actors will give the Cluster the strength to grow up further by integrating new value-added services and by establishing a virtuous circle involving also production sites (manufacturing). Moreover, in addition to the typical value added services (such as co-packing and shipment consolidation, late product differentiation, assembling and testing, logistics process tracking, vehicle load factor optimization, last mile optimization), taking advantage of CluCS as open platform, in the future new and innovative services related to physical transport could be offered, such as workshop services for locomotives and rail wagon maintenance and repair. These services could benefit from PTN logic.

According to this idea, shippers could use CluCS platform not only to book LSPs services but also to publish their specialized services and to be contacted via Access Point technology by manufacturers or generic customers that need to transfer goods (often to and from abroad) and to be supported to manage the necessary customs and fiscal procedures as well.

CluCS has been already designed to support shippers in finding the most suitable means of transport, suggesting also cargo consolidation and cargo pooling opportunities and in future could evolve as a paperless environment to manage commercial invoice, shipper's export declaration, bill of lading and other documents required by the carrier or country of export, import, and/or transshipment.

In Bologna PTN there are two principal manufacturing: P&G and Ceramiche Caesar that could be involved in an experimental scenario.

P&G, being one of the largest consumer products companies in the world, generates economies of scale through the integration of different brands, activities, operations and people.

P&G is a brand leader company. Focusing in Italy on 10 product categories with about 65 brands. The main 10 categories include Baby Care, Fabric Care, Family Care, Feminine Care, Grooming, Hair Care, Home Care, Oral Care, Personal Health Care, and Skin and Personal Care. Among the 10 categories, P & G includes 21 brands with annual sales ranging between 1 and 10 billion dollars and 11 brands that generate revenues between 500 million and 1 billion dollars. P&G has one industrial plant within the Bologna PTN area located to Gattatico (RE) – Parma Local Terminal Area.

Ceramiche Caesar, a company that is part of the Gruppo Concorde, is one of the leading ceramic tile holdings in the world, and with an annual production of more than 6 million square meters of porcelain stoneware, exports its products to more than 90 countries and has branch-offices in Italy, the USA and the UK offering a product range of more than 4,000 items, with a thickness ranging up to 20mm, available in 32 sizes and various surface finishes designed to meet different lifestyles and architectural needs.

Ceramiche Caesar has its main Industrial Plant within the Bologna PTN area located to Fiorano Modenese (MO) – Marzaglia Local Terminal Area.

4.1 Experimental scenario of VALS: cargo pooling

P&G and Ceramiche Caesar are the perfect candidate to take advantage of the valued added services that could be offered by CluCS platform such as cargo pooling opportunities: industries like P&G are likely to ship very light goods wasting weight capacity and, on the contrary, industries like Ceramiche Caesar are likely to ship very heavy goods wasting volume capacity. In other words, when P&G fills a truck (or a cargo unit) to the maximum possible volume, then the utilized weight capacity is only a part of the total, while when Ceramiche Caesar fills a truck (or a cargo unit) to the maximum permitted weight, then the utilized volume is only a part of the total.

Certainly, Ceramiche Caesar basic need's is to ship ceramic tile from its industrial plant in Modena Area to many destinations, and for this operation it will be supported by CluCS platform that will permit to insert request detailing quantity and information about containers, desired departure times and frequency of shipments. Similar requests could be done by Procter & Gamble that needs to ship mass consumption products from its industrial plant in Parma Regional Terminal area.

In planning phase CluCS engine works in the identification of cargo pooling opportunities at PTN/Cluster level and to present it to the PTN Manager, who, in turn, should contact the shippers to make the proposal. If the shippers accept, the execution phase starts as the cargo pooling agreed process.

CluCS platform can support this kind of optimization because it was designed to take in account overall information about cargo flows within the PTN/Cluster and also data regarding all offered logistic services. For our experimental scenario it is supposed that both P&G and Ceramiche Caesar are searching through CluCS platform transport services and they have in common at least a part of the logistic corridor.

As recap, the main scope of cargo pooling services therefore is the reduction of idle cargo capacity optimizing or reducing the use of vehicles and/or cargo units (containers, semitrailers, swap bodies, etc.) where, as it is known, volume and weight are the two principal factors to be considered.

In Bologna PTN thanks the use of CluCS platform there are all conditions to achieve this kind of optimization because:

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- manufacturing like P&G are likely to ship very light goods wasting weight capacity and they would like to overcome these limits
- manufacturing like Ceramiche Caesar are likely to ship very heavy goods wasting volume capacity and they would like to overcome these limits
- local and main terminals within the PTN can act as service providers in charge of the activity of pooling cargo
- LSPs acting in the PTN can provide the transport services needed
- CluCS works as a tool to identify cases of potential load factor optimization and getting in contact the different stakeholders involved as shown by the following high-level diagram flow

Figure 25 Cargo Pooling process

5 Definition of Smart Clusters development path [Leader: IBI; Partners: ZLC]

In this chapter the framework is proposed for Smart Clusters development. The framework should be based on a synergy between organizational (orgware) innovation aspect (CluCS organizational network built) and software (CluCS platform built) innovation aspect.

The most important prerequisites for building the Cluster&PTN network and full utilization of CluCS potentials are:

- Ensured willingness of all actors for risk, cost and profit sharing;
- Ensured willingness of all actors for information sharing.

Framework for setting up and maintaining the proposed Smart cluster should be based on a following multi step approach:

1. **Legal framework design** which includes:

- Creating incentive schemes for promoting sustainable and intermodal transport against a pure road transport;
- Incentives for improving the service quality of terminals within the Cluster and PTN, improving the last mile access and, minimizing the transshipment impedance and efficiency of rail sector;
- Support initiatives for uniform data management within Cluster&PTN.

2. **Research and innovation (R&I).** R&I represents an enabler for moving the current intra cluster system (highly fragmented flows – shipments from different shippers sent mainly by trucks without a system of flow consolidation) towards a more supply chain-oriented approach (efficient coordination of flows enhanced by cargo pooling and cargo consolidation). Sound research, development and innovation policies made by various recognized research and academic institutions have to bring proposed solution to the market.

3. **Strategic positioning.** This step includes initiating, building and maintaining the Supply Chain Oriented (SCO) business vision and mission within Cluster & PTN.

SCO as an important precondition for Smart Cluster development represents a shared value and belief system that aids in understanding how the organization should strategically manage its supply chain and behavioral norms inside the organization.

- The strategic SCO perspective involves encouraging an organization to take a systems approach to viewing supply chain holistically rather than as constituent parts and seeking integration, synchronization and convergence of intra and inter organization operational and strategic capabilities (Esper et al., 2010).
- The structural SCO perspective emphasizes organizational aspects that facilitate SCM. According to this perspective SCO should involve building and maintaining internal behavioral elements that facilitate relational exchange. Focus should be on the behavioral dimensions of trust, commitment, organizational compatibility, cooperative norms and top management support as elements of SCO (Min and Mentzer, 2004). Behaviors are defined in the context of SCO as cultural elements that support the organization's structure and require top management enforcement (Min et al., 2007).

According to this viewpoint, a supply chain oriented organisation not only places emphasis on systemic, integrated SCM, but also aligns this strategic thrust with an organisational structure that capitalizes on this strategy.

In other words, after having gone through the phase of strategic positioning all actors in a potential collaborative network will know what they can expect (motives), how they can benefit from the

innovation (objectives) and whether the engagement in the network will be more or less intensive (strategic, tactical or operational level).

Besides the contextual drivers for cooperation we have to emphasize the main motives – essential drivers for participating in established CLuCS:

- Presence of coordinator – PTN Manager as an intermediary who is in position to coordinate all activities within the established CluCS network.
- Drivers for cooperative action – Consider the already existing problems on a Logistics Cluster level and resource needs and interests (financial performances, economy of scope, scale, density).
- Interdependence – individual actors in the Clusters are unable to cope with existing issues in freight transportation.
- Uncertainty – uncertainty present in everyday business of LSP/VALS providers, terminal operators, shippers, railway can drive them to engage in CluCS in order to reduce, diffuse and share risk.

4. CluCS network design. In the CluCS establishment phase it is needed to take into account following stages:

- CluCS network engagement;
- Business case and financial mechanism of the cooperation;
- Strategy and vision of cooperation;
- Design of the shape of cooperation.

CluCS network engagement. Engagement of stakeholders with different goals to solve problems and create value – Important for the CluCS network is to define who the partners are. Good strategy which gains maximum synergy effects must be chosen for selecting the potential stakeholders in all cases when a choice exists.

Besides the forming of the network, engagement of stakeholders involves the following iterative processes:

- Evaluating the individual interests of every stakeholder;
- Continuous effort to build shared meaning by articulating the common purpose and objectives, clarifying tasks and expectations;
- Examination of issues and different perspectives of stakeholders involved;
- Alignment of different interests and conflict resolution.

Business case and financial mechanism of the engagement in CluCS network. Positive business case is necessary requirement for engagement of stakeholders. Positive business case will exist if there is a synergy within the CluCS network. Synergy means the positive difference between the cost if engagement and the cost of standing alone for each of the actors. Therefore, it is needed to quantify the qualitative engagement idea. This can be done by using the operational research tools.

Strategy and vision of CluCS network. Clear strategy and vision of cooperation are crucial for establishment of a stable and long lasting relationship.

Design of the shape of engagement. Here, the most important format of engagement need to be selected based on the drivers and objectives identified.

5. Implementation of CluCS network. Here, contractual framework within CluCS network and CluCS investment should be realized. Contract design should be based on criteria that provide an environment of trust. Trust will contribute to overcoming initial suspiciousness about potential partner opportunism which may prevent effective implementation of this vertical cooperation. Imbalances in organizational power, indicated by disparities in the resources contributed and controlled by the partners can impede trust creation due to the partner's unequal capacities to fulfil their obligations. More specifically, between all parties and PTN Manager a well specified contract should exist which encourages their engagement and trust. In case of absence of previous experience (where trust and relational norms are not well developed) contracts should be more formal in order to complement relational governance by providing the confidence for each of the partners through safeguarding transaction specific investments (in case there are – IT

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infrastructure, freight wagons) and controlling opportunism.

The second part of the CluCS network implementation represents design, development and implementation of the CluCS platform itself. CluCS platform can be viewed as a relationship specific asset in which case a proper alignment of interests of all involved actors must be performed, or as a service platform provided by PTN Manager. Existing systems of individual actors must also be integrated on some way into the platform in order to empower it with a full capability. The system should not be treated as a closed form system but contrary as a solution which needs to be continuously upgraded.

- 6. Orchestration.** Orchestration includes moderating the CluCS network. Efficient moderation must contain adaptive feature. This feedback mechanism should be based on permanent monitoring of defined (agreed by all partners) KPIs. KPIs represent indicators of the success of the cooperative relationship. They have the ability to affect the trust and therefore initiate conflicts that can have an impact on the longevity of established network. Conflicts can be avoided or reduced by organizing face to face meetings and designing appropriate agreements between stakeholders.

6 Conclusion

This report, elaborated within WP2, provides the guidelines for Smart Cluster establishment path, including engagement of manufacturing and value-added service providers in Cluster activities and integration of them with CluCS.

The deliverable is the result of task 2.5 in which the involvement of local actors in Cluster activities, thus the profitable engagement of manufacturing and value-added service providers, relying on CluCS capabilities for improving / enabling coordination and boosting logistics best practices has been realized.

The main objective of CluCS platform is to increase the performance of the existing network of flows between various nodes (hubs, terminals, warehouses) within the Logistics Cluster. This leads to the improvement of productivity of the cluster as a whole. CluCS represents a tool for all CluCS' actors, and above all for manufacturers and value-added service providers, for a smooth evolution from existing very dispersed technological panorama in a Cluster to a system based on the interconnection of a set of networks. It fits also with Physical Internet initiatives to tackle the inefficiencies in transport and logistics activities.

As regards the engagement of manufacturers in the platform, Cluster manager should create a comprehensive engagement strategy by reviewing and aligning motives and barriers of all actors, big firms, SMEs and convince them that the platform and the supply chain orientation approach may generate significant effects on their profitability and sustainability. Whereas, as regards value added logistics services integration, Cluster manager should play a facilitator role that enhances the development of collaboration practices and value-added services between co-located firms. The engagement strategy of manufacturers and value-added service providers should be materialized in a framework based on building the additional services in the earlier phase of customer demand chain (prior to transportation service).

CluCS concept needs very intensive and efficient cooperation between all involved stakeholders. However, interests of stakeholders are not fully aligned. In order to align the value cases of the most important stakeholders in CluCS network, the Value Case Methodology (VCM) has been applied. Bologna PTN main stakeholders have been identified and a stakeholders' analysis has been conducted using the information collected in a survey on CluCS implementation.

Shippers expect from CluCS better business results due to decreased service costs and a more visible, flexible and reliable service. Through the value-added service of cargo consolidation and cargo pooling transport capacities are better utilized, lead times are decreased and transport costs reduced. Whereas, VALS providers expect more engagement in intra- and inter- cluster related transport and logistics activities as a result of more intensive transportation and warehousing services which will improve responsiveness and decrease delays and waiting times at nodes.

On the other side, cost of participation to the CluCS network and for the IT system integration is a barrier for these stakeholders, due to their unwillingness to cooperate. For shippers the size of the costs depends whether they are a big manufacturer with their own IT system or a SME. LSP/VALS providers may consider also some costs for additional service provision (e.g. business process redesign) to satisfy client requests. Another barrier for both shippers and VALS providers is their unwillingness to share their information because they don't rely completely on CluCS.

In order to overcome these barriers, the motivation of the stakeholders who see the highest potential benefit in joining CluCS network could be used to convince other stakeholders with a less than acceptable benefit/risk ratio to support the concept. The 'driver' has to invest manpower/time into the project during the initial phase in order to convince stakeholders to join the platform.

According to the results of benefit/risk comparisons, it can be said that all stakeholders are motivated in some way to take the risk to join CluCS platform.

Finally, the Smart Clusters development path has been outlined. The most important prerequisites to build Cluster&PTN network and to assure a full utilization of CluCS potentials are: willingness of all actors for risk, cost, profit sharing and information sharing. The development path should be a multi-step approach based on a synergy between the organizational innovation aspect (CluCS organizational network) and the software innovation aspect (CluCS platform).

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7 Annexes

Annex A. Questionnaire responses from CluCS stakeholders

Stakeholder 1

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Railway company

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

Transporeon, Transwide, etc

- o If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

- o If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

Yes No

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

Quick information exchange; time optimization; data availability

3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

The services offered by CluCS are a good starting point.

4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

If the current company strategies are aimed at other sectors, departments.

5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?
6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?
Yes No
7. Would you be willing to adopt CluCS instead of your current methods to book and plan shipments?
Yes No
8. Would you be willing to become a CluCS node and therefore to share your data in order to become part of the network?
Yes No
9. Do you usually work with contractual frameworks for the provision of logistics services?
Yes No
 - If yes: Would you be willing to switch to short-term agreements via CluCS?
Yes No
10. Would you be willing to pay a little percentage fee on the total transaction for the service?
Yes No
11. For terminals:
Would you be willing to pay an annual fee for being on CluCS and therefore to benefit from its services?
Yes No

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Hub manager

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

- If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

- If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

Yes No

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

The possibility to integrate different transport modes and IT systems, having more visibility on the offered services and booking services. It could be a very useful service for all the settled companies in the hub community.

3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

Giving visibility to all transport modes; direct transport services booking; single ITU (Intermodal Transport Unit) traceability.

4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

There are no barriers

5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Road hauliers, shipping companies and terminal operators

6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?

Yes No

7. Would you be willing to adopt CluCS instead of your current methods to book and plan shipments?

Yes No

8. Would you be willing to become a CluCS node and therefore to share your data in order to become part of the network?

Yes No

9. Do you usually work with contractual frameworks for the provision of logistics services?

Yes No

- o If yes: Would you be willing to switch to short-term agreements via CluCS?

Yes No

10. Would you be willing to pay a little percentage fee on the total transaction for the service?

Yes No

11. For terminals:

Would you be willing to pay an annual fee for being on CluCS and therefore to benefit from its services?

Yes No

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Logistic Service Provider

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

○ If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

○ If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

Yes No

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

Slots and time optimization

3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

Rail and road transport integration.

4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

There are no barriers.

5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Road hauliers, shipping companies and terminal operators

6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?

Yes No

7. Would you be willing to adopt CluCS instead of your current methods to book and plan shipments?

Yes No

8. Would you be willing to become a CluCS node and therefore to share your data in order to become part of the network?

Yes No

9. Do you usually work with contractual frameworks for the provision of logistics services?

Yes No

- o If yes: Would you be willing to switch to short-term agreements via CluCS?

Yes No

10. Would you be willing to pay a little percentage fee on the total transaction for the service?

Yes No

11. For terminals:

Would you be willing to pay an annual fee for being on CluCS and therefore to benefit from its services?

Yes No

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Terminal manager

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

○ If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

○ If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

Yes No

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?
- Yes No
7. Would you be willing to adopt CluCS instead of your current methods to book and plan shipments?
- Yes No
- Not now
8. Would you be willing to become a CluCS node and therefore to share your data in order to become part of the network?
- Yes No
- Maybe, the opportunity should be better evaluated
9. Do you usually work with contractual frameworks for the provision of logistics services?
- Yes No
- If yes: Would you be willing to switch to short-term agreements via CluCS?
- Yes No
10. Would you be willing to pay a little percentage fee on the total transaction for the service?
- Yes No
11. For terminals:
Would you be willing to pay an annual fee for being on CluCS and therefore to benefit from its services?
- Yes No
- Not now
- N.B.** So far there are no advantages for my terminal. Obviously, becoming part of a network has to entail an availability of rail connections that are not present at the moment.

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Logistics Service Provider and Terminal manager

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

- o If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

The booking service only

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

Occasionally

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

- o If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

Yes No

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

It needs an adequate data network

3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?
5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Terminal and railway companies

6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?
Yes No
7. Would you be willing to adopt CluCS instead of your current methods to book and plan shipments?

Yes No

It depends

8. Would you be willing to become a CluCS node and therefore to share your data in order to become part of the network?

Yes No

9. Do you usually work with contractual frameworks for the provision of logistics services?

Yes No

- If yes: Would you be willing to switch to short-term agreements via CluCS?

Yes No

10. Would you be willing to pay a little percentage fee on the total transaction for the service?

Yes No

It depends.

11. For terminals:
Would you be willing to pay an annual fee for being on CluCS and therefore to benefit from its services?

Yes No

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Multimodal Traffic Operator (MTO)

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

Transporeon, Transwide, etc

- If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

The platform didn't quickly manage the train slots.

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

Because the train slots showed in the platform, were placed too slowly.

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

- If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

Yes No

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

The expected benefits are the quick transport services collocation that, otherwise, would be lost or unsuccessful.

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3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

It should collocate transport services very quickly. It has to present the offered services and the promotional offers clearly.

4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Difficulties in implementing an automatic data integration system.

5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Shippers, terminal operators, producers

6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?

Yes No

7. Would you be willing to adopt CluCS instead of your current methods to book and plan shipments?

Yes No

8. Would you be willing to become a CluCS node and therefore to share your data in order to become part of the network?

Yes No

9. Do you usually work with contractual frameworks for the provision of logistics services?

Yes No

- If yes: Would you be willing to switch to short-term agreements via CluCS?

Yes No

10. Would you be willing to pay a little percentage fee on the total transaction for the service?

Yes No

11. For terminals:

Would you be willing to pay an annual fee for being on CluCS and therefore to benefit from its services?

Yes No

Questionnaire – Clusters 2.0_Cluster Community System

1. Please indicate the type of entity for which you work (Shipper, Logistics Service Provider, Freight forwarder, Infrastructure (including hub managers), etc.):

Train operator, terminal operator and logistic provider

2. Have you ever used an IT platform that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Yes No

- If yes:

- Does/did the system cover your needs?

Yes No

Partially

- If no: What applications did it lack to make it relevant for your company?

At the moment mainly booking facilities are offered but no real on-time monitoring, ETA calculation and connection with infrastructure like terminal

- Do you still use this system?

Yes No

- If no: Why do you not use this system anymore?

- Did you experience any problems with implementing the use of this IT system?

Yes No

Not really and recent system are becoming more and more opened thanks to the API approach

- If yes: What problems did you experience with implementing the system?

- If no:

- Would your company consider using such an IT platform?

- If yes: What benefits would you expect to get out of using such a system?

3. What services do you consider that such an IT platform should provide in order to be relevant for your company?

Knowledge information on operations execution and products existing when you look for alternatives.

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4. What are the main barriers that you consider could prevent your company from using an IT system that provides intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

Added value we may have in such system compared to our booking system in order to compensate potential fees

5. What type of stakeholders would you consider relevant to share information with through an IT system that provides services such as intermodal service booking and/or cargo consolidation and cargo pooling?

All stakeholder of the supply chain are interested until they find an interest. Shipper and client to track the progress of the delivery, operator, first/last mile trucking company if they can have more business and reduce administrative transport tasks that may accelerate at the end the payment of the services

6. Do you consider that such an IT system optimize your company's logistics processes?

Yes No

It depends

Annex B. Participants' List – Interporto Bologna CluCS presentation event 12th June 2019

Clusters 2.0		Evento Presentazione CluCS 12/06/2019 Palazzina Doganale, Interporto Bologna	
No.	Nome	Azienda	Firma
1	MASSIMO BAGOTTI	DBA LAB SPA	
2	CRISTIAN MANTOVANI	PERCITALIA Int.	
3	MATTEO APOLLONIO	DBA LAB SPA	
4	CLAUDIO FRANCESCHELLI	OLIO EXPRESS	
5	ALESSANDRO BATTOCINI	T.E.R. SPA	
6	PAOLO PACANICCI	BLUVERDIEN	
7	TRACCHENTA BIANCHI	INTERPORTO - BOLOGNA HO	
8	LEONARDO STUCCI	STUCCI SRL	
9	MICHELE POGGI	CLBT / BERTESSON	
10	MARCO BENINI	INTERPORTO BOLOGNA	
11	MANUELA DI MARZO	CONSORZIO IB INNOVATION	
12	ALICE BENINI	CONSORZIO IB INNOVATION	
13	SENGIO CARSAI	IPBO	
14	ROBERTO TORZUCCIO	IPBO	
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			